

City blocks as living labs for sharing economy

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Abstract

While circular and sharing economy services are widely available at national and city levels, only a few apply directly to the city block level. In this presentation we explain how the circular and sharing economy has been promoted at the city block level by implementing co-creation activities and facilitating agile pilots in four pilot locations in the Helsinki region. The presentation provides insights from the living lab activities and how the learnings could be scaled-up.

Keywords

circular economy, sharing economy, sustainable urban living, action research, agile piloting, co-creation

Introduction

The current lifestyle and covid-19 pandemic have increased time spent at home. Simultaneously, the triple crisis calls for a rapid change in lifestyle and consumer habits (UNFCCC, 2022). As our daily environments, city blocks are essential for meeting CO2 objectives.

While circular and sharing economy services are widely available at national and city levels, only a few apply directly to the city block level. New business opportunities arise, but seizing them requires a better understanding of the target audience and diversity of block contexts—namely, a dialogue between companies and service users. The Circular Green Blocks project (Circular Green Blocks, 2023) raises awareness and coaches block level operators, such as housing associations, to implement circular and sharing economy solutions in their property and neighbourhoods. It also supports companies in developing their services to answer block-level needs.

Methods

The project utilises an action research approach and seeks a transformation through the simultaneous process of doing research, implementing co-creation activities, and facilitating pilots. Four pilot blocks including both rental and privately-owned premises in the Helsinki region (Finland) provide a living lab for the co-creation activities and pilots. Altogether the pilots affect forty residential buildings with nearly 500 apartments.

The project team facilitates co-creation and sharing economy pilots with residents and service providers, utilising the double diamond model of service design (Design Council, 2019; Pyykkö, Suoheimo, & Walter, 2021) and agile piloting program (Rinne & Spilling, 2020). The first phase focused on creating an in-depth understanding of each block: their context, development needs and challenges. These insights fed into launching two open calls for pilots of innovative sharing economy services from companies.

The second phase focused on piloting the selected solutions within the blocks. Five companies representing the sectors of the sharing economy, smart mobility and urban farming were chosen for the pilots. During a six-month period, the residents and housing associations tested shared electric bicycles, borrowing and sharing of goods, as well as communal urban gardening.

Throughout, the project team collected and analysed experiences to develop the services.

Results and take-aways

The needs identified during the first phase were overall similar in all pilot blocks with block-specific nuances that were specified further to 3-4 development tasks reflecting the context of each block. The pilots provided key learnings on sharing in city blocks and enabled the development of the solutions. The companies gained experience from a new customer segment and received first-hand feedback from their services.

A short piloting period allows companies a low threshold to test solutions with a new target group. Residents' outreach and communication about pilots were found challenging, which may have affected negatively on the utilisation rate during the piloting. However, the adoption of a new service takes time and a full picture of demand and residents' needs and desires may not become visible in a short time.

In our presentation we will provide the public with learnings from the living lab activities run in the city blocks as well as insights from the sharing economy pilots and how the learnings could be scaled-up. We also aim to gain new insights on the applicability of the project's methods and results on the international contexts, and learn how the block level circular and sharing economy has been addressed in other cities and neighbourhoods.

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